

ECO-FRIENDLY AND LARGE-SCALE FABRICATION OF MICROELECTRONIC SILK-BASED ENZYMATIC BIOSENSORS

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ABSTRACT

Silk fibroin (SF) from *Bombyx mori* is emerging as a sustainable biomaterial for enzyme-based biosensors due to its ability to stabilize enzyme activity and provide a robust matrix for biomolecule immobilization. Despite its integration into micro- and nanofabrication workflows remains underexplored. This study presents a novel, eco-friendly approach for integrating SF into cleanroom microelectronic workflows by depositing and processing SF at wafer level.

Uniform SF films with tunable thicknesses ranging from 59 ± 5 to 131 ± 2 nm were spin-coated onto silicon wafers and precisely patterned via electron beam lithography (EBL) using an optimized exposure dose of $1200 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. Water was employed as the sole developer, avoiding the use of toxic organic solvents conventionally used in lithographic processes. SEM imaging confirmed high-resolution nano-patterning, with accurate and uniform hole sizes of 200 ± 2 nm. Enzymatic activity assays demonstrated that glucose oxidase (GOx) encapsulated in SF films retained over 90% activity after vacuum water annealing and 75% after chemically-mediated curing using green chemical compounds (GCC), representing a ~260-200% improvement over conventional methanol-based curing methods, which has previously limited the application of SF as a bio-modified photoresist in microelectronic biosensor fabrication. Notably, enzymatic activity measured after EBL exposure indicated that the lithographic process did not compromise the enzyme integrity.

This protocol enables the scalable fabrication of a novel bio-functional photoresist based on SF combining precise patterning while ensuring enzyme stability, positioning SF as a sustainable material for next-generation biosensor and bioelectronic devices, and eliminating the need for hazardous chemicals in cleanroom fabrication.

KEYWORDS

Silk technologies, wafer-level processing, biosensors production, microelectronics, spin-coating, photoresist, electron beam lithography (EBL), eco-friendly microfabrication.

INTRODUCTION

Silk-based Biosensors Through Microelectronics

SF, derived from the cocoons of *Bombyx mori* silkworm, is a biomaterial with exceptional properties, including biocompatibility, biodegradability, mechanical

stability, and chemical resistance. These characteristics have positioned it as a promising material for various applications in biomedicine, tissue engineering, and biomedical devices [1]. In a microelectronic point of view, SF is compatible with multiple microfabrication technologies, including photolithography [2], soft-lithography [3], electron-beam lithography [4] and laser ablation [5], among others, where SF-based technologies are fully “green” and water-based (in opposition to conventional resists that require solvents and UV irradiation).

On the other hand, SF has garnered increasing interest in the development of enzyme-based biosensors due to its ability to preserve enzyme activity and provide a stable matrix for biomolecule immobilization [6]. However, the scalable production of silk-based biosensors at wafer level using microelectronic technologies has not been demonstrated yet.

Here, a novel approach has been proposed that integrates enzymatically-doped SF resists into microelectronic manufacturing workflows, using photolithography and electron beam lithography (EBL) in an all water-based process carried out entirely at wafer level. These techniques, widely used in the semiconductor industry, enable the creation of micro- and nanoscale structures with high precision, facilitating the production of biosensors with superior structural control and enhanced compatibility with advanced electronic platforms [7,8]. This innovation opens new possibilities for the development of high-performance and environmentally friendly biomedical devices.

Electron Beam Lithography for High-Precision Patterning of SF film

The polymorphic nature of self-assembled SF matrices allows their use as a water based positive or negative resist for photolithography, very demanded as alternatives to the commonly used ones that involve toxic organic solvents as developers. Procedure consists of spin coating the aqueous SF solution, which allows the formation of a film of controlled thickness. Silk fibroin (SF) films are initially water-soluble due to their predominantly amorphous structure. However, they can be rendered water-insoluble during the curing process by inducing crystallization, which leads to the formation of highly ordered β -sheet domains within the protein matrix. This structural transition enables the selective patterning of SF films, allowing differentiation between crystallized regions (positive resist) and amorphous regions (negative resist) [4]. As positive one, inelastic collisions of electrons with

cured films result in the degradation of SF protein and formation of short water-soluble polypeptides that can be washed away during the water development. For negative resist cases, high electron beam doses are needed, resulting in the amorphous-to-helix folding of SF and enabling the formation of intermolecular crosslinks which makes the protein water-insoluble [2]. Therefore, following water development promotes the solubilization of the amorphous SF, except in areas exposed to electron beam, where the induced cross-linking stabilizes the SF structure, preventing its dissolution.

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Material Fabrication

A 6.4% (w/v) SF solution was prepared in Milli-Q water and GOx (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was added to reach a final concentration of 1% (w/w) GOx/SF. The mixture was thoroughly homogenized, and 4 ml were deposited onto a silicon or glass substrate (Ted Pella, USA), followed by spin coating (Laurell Technologies, USA) at 4000 rpm for 3 minutes and drying at room temperature. The dried films were then sectioned into 4x4 mm chips using a diamond tip cutter.

Three curing methods were tested: (1) vacuum water annealing under controlled temperature and pressure using a vacuum desiccator (Across International, USA), (2) methanol (MeOH) (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) immersion, and (3) the addition of a GCC, which induced direct β -sheet domains formation in a single drying step. After drying, the cured films underwent electron beam (e-beam) exposure using an EBL system (RAITH 150 model). Different doses ranging from 300 to 600000 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ were tested to determine the optimal one. Subsequently, circular arrays and square patterns were fabricated under specific conditions of energy (30 keV), apertures, current, and step size. The exposed samples were then developed by immersion in Milli-Q water for 2 minutes to remove unexposed regions. Finally, microscopy (Zeiss, Germany), spectroscopy (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), was used to assess structural analysis and functionality. Figure 1 illustrates the fabrication workflow. All steps were conducted under controlled environmental conditions to preserve enzyme activity, ensuring uniform coating, controlled fibroin curing, and accurate patterning. The processed films were stored in dry conditions at 4°C until further use.

Figure 1: Schematic of the enzyme-based biosensor fabrication protocol. The process involves doping the SF solution with glucose oxidase, depositing it onto a silicon wafer via spin coating, sectioning the wafer into chips, fibroin curing and nanoscale patterning on SF film.

Physicochemical and Structural Characterization

Characterization was performed at the Institute of Microelectronics of Barcelona (IMB-CNM-CSIC). EBL-patterned samples were analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, 1560XB and Auriga-40 models, Carl Zeiss) at a working distance (WD) of 2–6 mm, electron high tension (EHT) of 2–3 kV, and magnifications of 15kX to 40kX. The accuracy of EBL patterns was assessed using atomic force microscopy (AFM, Bruker Icon) and focused ion beam (FIB) techniques, providing nanoscale surface topography. FIB analysis was conducted at WD = 5.1 mm, EHT = 2 kV, magnifications of 50kX to 200kX, with cross-sectioning at 30kV:20pA or 30kV:50pA. SF layer thickness was measured using reflectometry (Nanospec 6100, IMB-CNM cleanroom) under various conditions. Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy (Invenio-S IR spectrometer, Bruker) was used to confirm β -sheet domains formation in SF films on 4-inch silicon wafers

Biological Activity Evaluation

3,3',5,5'-Tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) - horseradish peroxidase (HRP) coupled assay protocol described by Lu et al. [8] was adapted to quantify enzymatic activity loss during the process. First, 50 μL of a 1% (w/v) TMB solution in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) (Fisher Chemical, USA) was added to 6 mL of phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). The substrate solution was prepared by mixing 6 mL of TMB solution with 0.75 mL of 18% (w/v) glucose and 0.25 mL of 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ HRP (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) in PBS. Aliquots of 200 μL of substrate solution were added to a 96-well plate, and chips (4 replicates per condition) were immersed. The plate was incubated for 5 minutes to allow GOx activity, followed by the addition of 100 μL of 0.1 M sulfuric acid (Carlo Erba Reagents, Spain) to stop the reaction and reduce TMB. Absorbance was measured at 450 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Varioskan Flash, Thermo Scientific, USA). The absorbance values were normalized by the chip area (using ImageJ software) and compared to the control samples at the initial time to calculate the percentage of activity lost during the curing process and EBL patterning steps.

In this assay, GOx (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) catalyses the oxidation of glucose to D-glucono- δ -lactone and hydrogen peroxide. HRP (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) then catalyses the redox reaction from TMB and hydrogen peroxide to oxidized TMB and water, producing a colour change from colourless to blue, then yellow upon acidification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Film Thickness Optimization

Thickness characterization of the SF films fabricated by spin coating revealed values between 59 ± 5 to 131 ± 2 nm, depending on the coating conditions. This thickness can be controlled modifying several factors such as SF concentration in the initial solution, spin rate and GCC doping. Table 1 shows the values of SF layer thickness obtained for the different conditions tested. We can observe that, keeping all other conditions constant, as we increase the spinning speed from 3000 rpm to 6000 rpm, the layer thickness decreases, from 125 ± 11 to 72 ± 6 respectively

for a fibroin concentration of 7.3% w/v. Another effect to consider is the GCC doping. Doping at the concentration used in this work (20% v/v) increases thickness from 59 ± 5 to 107 ± 5 for a constant fibroin concentration of 6.4% w/v, due to the increase in the viscosity of the doped solution. The values obtained also show a proportionally relationship between the square root of the SF viscosity and film thickness. These values range from 59 ± 5 to 131 ± 2 for fibroin concentrations between 6.4% and 8.2% w/v respectively. SF films, with controlled thicknesses between 59 ± 5 to 131 ± 2 nm, depending on the coating conditions, were fabricated using the spin-coating technique onto silicon wafers, demonstrating the versatility adaptability of the process.

Table 1: Thickness obtained in SF layers using different spin coating conditions. Thickness measurements were performance with Nanospec 6100.

Time (s)	Speed (rpm)	Fibroin (%w/v)	GCC Addition	Thickness (nm)
180	3000	7,3	-	125 ± 11
	4000	6,4	-	59 ± 5
			+ 20% GCC for fibroin curing.	107 ± 5
		7,3	-	109 ± 7
		8,2	-	131 ± 2
	6000	7,3	-	72 ± 6

Spin rate of 4000 rpm and a 6.4 % SF concentration were selected as standard conditions to fabricate layers approximately 59 nm thick for the remaining tests, ensuring consistent samples.

Electron Beam Lithography Optimization

Exposure Dose

Once the film thickness of the samples was selected, optimal EBL exposure doses were optimized in order not to damage areas in an unspecific way, which could damage the enzyme and the SF layer.

Figure 2: (A) Optical microscopy images of SF film patterns exposed to EBL at doses ranging from 300 to 60,000 $\mu\text{C}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. (B) SEM image of a patterned structure edge (dose 4.0), with an AFM height profile on the right showing height differences between exposed and unexposed regions, varying from -20 nm to 80 nm.

In Figure 2A, optical microscope images of same EBL patterned SF film areas using different exposure doses designed as dose 1.0 (300 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$), 2.0 (600 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$), 4.0 (1200 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$), 10 (3000 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$), 20 (6000 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$), 40 (12000 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$), 100 (30000 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$) and 200 (60000 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$). It can be clearly observed that at doses below 2.0, there is a surface alteration, but it is not enough to remove the layer completely. On the other hand, at higher doses (>4), overexposure seems to occur, causing a loss of precision in layer removal and even affecting unexposed

areas. Figure 2B shows an SEM image of the edge of the 4.0 dose patterning and on the right an AFM measurement associated with the unevenness caused by the pattern. This measurement, unlike the other doses, revealed for dose 4.0 a difference between the exposed and non-exposed zones of approximately 50 nm, which ensures almost total elimination of the SF layer, and zero degradation of the zones close to the irradiated zone. This dose was therefore chosen as the optimum dose for the process.

Patterning Resolution

As introduced, once the dose was fixed at 600 $\mu\text{C}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, circular patterns with a diameter of approximately 200 nm and with a gap (edge to edge) of 200 nm were successfully fabricated. Figure 3 shows SEM images of the resulting patterned arrays (A) and its cross-sectional FIB view (B). The combined use of SEM and FIB allowed for the verification of well-defined and accurately resolved pattern.

Figure 3. SEM images of EBL-patterned SF films. Image A features 200 nm diameter holes, with a spacing of 200 nm between each other. FIB cross-sectional view was used to verify correct hole formation in image B. Scale bar = 200 nm.

Enzymatic stability studies

Enzymatic activity retention during process

Once the process was optimized and the structural properties of the material were evaluated, a biochemical characterization was carried out to determine the biosensing capacity and the activity of the enzyme encapsulated in the SF films during the manufacturing protocol. For this purpose, retained percentage of enzymatic activity during the fibroin curing step and EBL, the most critical steps for the enzyme viability, were studied. In Figure 4, images corresponding to the colour change and retained GOx activity in SF chips after the different curing protocols and the EBL patterning (in this case is only considered the unexposed area), taking the amorphous chips samples as the positive control (100% of enzyme activity). The obtained data indicate that vacuum water annealing effectively preserves enzymatic activity, retaining approximately 90%, making it the most suitable method for curing films in terms of enzymatic viability. In contrast, MeOH immersion proves to be a highly aggressive treatment that significantly compromises enzyme stability even at short times, with activities below 30% after 30 seconds of immersion and practically fully inactivated (0% activity) after 5 minutes, being consistent with other previous results [9]. On the other hand, GCC-mediated curing maintains approximately 75% of the enzymatic activity. These results suggest the potential of GCC as an alternative to the use of more cost and time-consuming vacuum water annealing protocols and organic

Figure 4: Images of the TMB-HRP assay showing the retained enzymatic activity at different stages of the biosensor fabrication process: (A) silicon + silicon oxide (SiO_2) substrate, (B) deposition of silk fibroin via spin coating, (C) silk film curing using different protocols, and (D) EBL patterning.

solvents such as MeOH, which drastically compromise enzyme activity. Furthermore, chips exposed to EBL (cured for 30 seconds in MeOH immersion), show a retention of enzyme activity of about 30% (after area correction), the same value as after crystallization, thus demonstrating that the EBL patterning process is not harmful to the enzyme present in the non-irradiated areas of the SF-based photoresist, confirming its suitability for biosensors scalability using microelectronic technologies.

CONCLUSIONS

This study introduces a ground-breaking approach to fabricating SF-based enzymatic biosensors at wafer level, combining a green crystallization protocol, superior enzyme stability, and high-resolution patterning.

The novel protocol developed eliminates the use of organic solvents, in both crystallization and development steps, and cuts down the production time significantly, reducing the environmental impact of the biosensor fabrication and without compromising enzymatic activity throughout the entire process. The process ensures the reproducible and scalable fabrication of bio-resist with controlled thickness, crystallization and patterning in a process carried out entirely in cleanroom environment and at wafer level, making them suitable for applications in biosensors and bioelectronics.

High-resolution EBL patterning opens new possibilities for high-performance devices suitable for point-of-care diagnostics, environmental pollutant detection, and industrial biocatalysis monitoring. By integrating SF into cleanroom-compatible workflows, this method advances the field of eco-friendly microelectronics and bridge the gap between biomaterials and semiconductor technologies.

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